

DECODING POLITICAL LANGUAGE: CONCEPTUAL METAPHORS AND THEIR DISCURSIVE FUNCTIONS

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>Conceptual metaphor has been widely acknowledged as a critical rhetorical device for achieving persuasive effects in political discourse. This study proposes a new and comprehensive perspective that directly analyzes the possible reasons for the occurrence of conceptual metaphors and their impacts from three interconnected dimensions of discourse: “textual”, “discursive practice”, and “social practice”. Furthermore, to assess the feasibility of this framework, the study conducts a comparative analysis of two political speeches delivered by the Australian prime minister Antony Albanese, which serve as a typical form of political discourse, aiming to investigate the similarities and differences in the conceptual metaphors employed, as well as the underlying causes and roles. The analysis reveals that both speeches frequently utilize structural and ontological metaphors, while orientational metaphors are rarely employed. Additionally, the two speeches exhibit significant overlap in their use of specific metaphors, such as the JOURNEY metaphor. This similarity can be analyzed from multiple perspectives within this framework since there are resemblances between the two speeches such as genre, general topic, the process of discourse production and distribution. The variance across three dimensions in the two speeches also results in variations in metaphor selection. This research contributes to Conceptual Metaphor Analysis (CMA) by developing an integrative approach that bridges textual semantics with cognitive processes and social contexts. The proposed framework not only elucidates the socio-cognitive motivations underlying metaphorical choices but also demonstrates how such linguistic devices mediate between political ideology and public perception.</p>	<p>critical metaphor analysis, conceptual metaphor, critical discourse analysis, political speech, metaphor purposes</p>

1. Introduction

Metaphor is considered the most widely and frequently used rhetorical device in English. The study of metaphor can be traced back to the time of Aristotle. In 1980, Lakoff and Johnson published their monograph *Metaphors We Live By*, which linked metaphor with cognition for the first time and initiated a new paradigm for metaphor research. They proposed that metaphor is a universal cognitive pattern and a way of understanding the world. The

essence of metaphor is understanding and experiencing one kind of thing in terms of another (Kramsch et al, 2004, p. 125). Later, Lakoff (1993) elaborated on the conceptual metaphor theory and proposed that metaphor is a systematic mapping from one conceptual domain to another, which are called the “source domain” and the “target domain” respectively.

Political discourse is a type of discourse that is considered to possess a strong sense of purpose (Tian, 2002), typically employing a set of either linguistic or non-linguistic approaches, such as rhetorical devices, discursive strategies, or speech acts, to influence the audience’s understanding and evaluation of certain issue, achieving the ultimate goal of persuasion. Among those, rhetoric, as Charteris-Black (2005, p.8) points out, is considered as the art of persuasion, since any definition of rhetoric inherently encompasses the notion of influencing others’ beliefs or actions. This connection is particularly evident in the realm of political communication, where politicians are becoming increasingly aware of the power of metaphors. He also pointed that metaphors play a crucial role in political discourse, especially during elections and when discussing policy-related issues. By leveraging metaphors, politicians can make their messages more compelling and persuasive. The development of cognitive semantics offers a fresh perspective for studying political discourse. Thus, conceptual metaphors, which are often employed to make political speeches and texts more engaging and persuasive, have gathered significant attention. These metaphors are designed to capture the audience’s interest and ultimately secure their support and votes.

Influenced by Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA), in 2004, Charteris-Black first proposed Critical Metaphor Analysis (CMA) in his monograph *Corpus Approaches to Critical Metaphor Analysis*. As a method of metaphor analysis, CMA combines various research fields such as critical discourse analysis, corpus linguistics, pragmatics, and cognitive linguistics. It is considered as a complement to critical discourse analysis, which aims to examine the conceptual metaphors within political discourse, revealing the underlying intentions, ideologies, and political attitudes of discourse producers (2004, 2013). Scholars have indicated that political discourse is constructed in a way that the rhetoric is recontextualized to serve the purposes for which the text is produced, manipulated, and intended to be interpreted by the discourse producers or orators (Minoo et al, 2018). Despite Charteris-Black (2013) suggests seven possible purposes of metaphors, there remains an absence of a systematic analytical approach dedicated to examining the metaphor use in political discourse. This highlights the need for a more nuanced understanding of how metaphors operate within the complicated landscape of political communication. The innovative perspective proposed integrates the three dimensions of CDA suggested by Norman Fairclough (1992) into the CMA theory, which analyzes the potential reasons for the emergence of conceptual metaphors and their impacts directly from the three levels of discourse, “textual, discursive practice, and social practice”. This multi-dimensional analytical approach provides deeper insights into the use of metaphors in political discourse, thereby advancing the study of political metaphors. Furthermore, the current study elaborates on the rationale behind this analytical framework and discusses its application across a diverse range of aspects. Besides, to assess the feasibility of this framework, the study examines two political speeches delivered by the same politician in different situations, and compares the conceptual metaphors employed in these two speeches, investigating the similarities and differences in the conceptual metaphors used, as well as the intentions behind them. This study offers a new perspective for CMA, and this analytical perspective facilitates more integrated analysis of conceptual metaphors, linking the meaning of text with cognition and society.

The three questions aim to be addressed in current study.

A. What types of conceptual metaphors are employed in two speeches respectively?

B. What are the similarities and differences in the types and categories of conceptual metaphors used in two speeches?

C. What are the reasons behind these similarities and differences, and what roles do the metaphors employed in speeches play?

2. Critical Metaphor Analysis in Political Discourse

In 1980, the publication of the monograph *Metaphors We Live By* (Lakoff & Johnson, 1980) marked a significant milestone. Since then, it has been widely recognized that metaphors are not merely linguistic elements serving as rhetorical devices in texts or speeches, but they also convey conceptual content. Lakoff categorized conceptual metaphors into three types: structural metaphors, ontological metaphors, and orientational metaphors. Based on the conceptual metaphor theory, Charteris-Black (2004) introduced “Critical Metaphor Analysis”, which incorporates cognitive linguistics, semantics and pragmatics, and corpus analysis into the study of metaphors, paving a new way for discourse analysis. This approach has been widely applied to the analysis of discourse involving politics, economics (e.g., Chen & Qiu, 2022), education (e.g., Ren, 2022), ecology (e.g., Tang, 2024), and even multimodal elements such as comics (e.g., Zhao & Wu, 2024).

Extensive CMA research has been conducted in the realm of political discourse, with one of the focuses on news coverage of significant events (e.g., Han, 2014; Leo, 2020; Yu et al, 2022; Yang, 2023; Truc, 2024). For instance, since 2019, the analysis of COVID-19 news coverage has gathered particular attention (e.g., Leo, 2020; Truc, 2024). Political speeches, as a typical genre of political discourse, have been extensively studied, particularly those delivered by specific politicians or national leaders worldwide, such as speeches by U.S. presidents (e.g., Ahrens et al., 2011; Pilyarchuk & Onysko, 2018), Japan’s current Prime Minister Fumio Kishida (e.g., Sun & Tao, 2024), or leaders of some African countries (Agbo et al., 2018). Regarding the CMA on speeches, many scholars have also conducted comparative studies of two or more speeches, including diachronic analysis (e.g., Malan, 2008; Hu, 2010; Ruan, 2015), differences in metaphor use between different political parties or groups within one country (e.g., Ivanovic, 2017; Yan, 2022; Jin & Yu, 2023), and speeches delivered by politicians from different nations (e.g., Weng, 2013). Previous research on metaphors in political discourse has often concentrated on classifying and interpreting metaphors within specific corpora, aiming to analyze the types of metaphors used in speeches and how politicians employ them to effectively convey their messages and influence their audiences. Considering the relationship between metaphor and CDA, most studies have focused on the complementary role of metaphor analysis to CDA (Hart, 2011; Musolff, 2012; Farahani & Adeli, 2019), while overlooking the possibility of leading the analysis of metaphors from the aspects of discourse. Previous studies have suggested that conceptual metaphors are regarded as a direct connection between meaning and cognition. In other words, the meaning of words is interpreted and understood through organized fragments of knowledge within an individual’s cognition. This connection, in addition to being realized by means of metaphor, can also be embodied in other aspects of discourse or sentence structure, such as modalities and evidentiality (Van Dijk, 2014). Conversely, within the field of critical metaphor analysis, CDA primarily offers a perspective focused on political attitudes and ideology for conducting metaphorical analysis. For example, Jafarnezhad’s study (2023) employed Kovecses’ framework to examine the role of metaphor in a decade of political journals concerning Iran-West relations. The most representative study is Charteris-Black’s (2014) revision of his previous theory of CMA, which incorporates different perspectives of CDA, including the Discourse-historical Approach developed by Wodak. He outlines various approaches to analyzing political speeches and proposes different analytical

perspectives for interpreting metaphors. However, his proposal to add contextual analysis as a preliminary step in CMA in that research lacks a detailed explanation of its rationale.

It must be pointed that, the illuminating role of specific CDA frameworks, such as Fairclough's three-dimensional model, which originated from the three-dimensional nature of discourse, has been neglected in CMA. Despite the abundance of empirical research on discourse and power, it is imperative to prioritize the integration of discourse with cognition and society (Van Dijk, 2015). The guidance provided by CDA offers a prolific space for cognitive linguistics

(Charteris-Black, 2004).

2.1 Rationale for Introducing Three Dimensions of CDA to Analysis of CMA

When examining the roles that conceptual metaphors play in political discourse, insights can be drawn from the research perspectives used in CDA. The integration of the three dimensions of discourse in CDA, as proposed by Fairclough, into the CMA theory is justified for several reasons.

Firstly, both CMA and CDA are fundamentally concerned with the analysis of discourse. Metaphors are embedded in the text, constituting an essential component of the discourse. In the realm of political discourse, CMA usually focuses on the role of metaphors that serve to simplify abstract political ideas, communicate the ideologies of states and politicians, and persuade the public to adopt certain viewpoints or policies. To achieve these purposes, those who employ metaphors, or the discourse providers, may consider a multitude of factors when constructing their messages. These factors can be concluded into the various elements within CDA's three dimensions: the textual, the discursive practices, and the social practices (Fairclough, 1992). He further argues that discourse, as a social practice, should be investigated not merely for its textual components and the shared sociocultural knowledge it conveys, but also for its deeper societal structures and contexts. By integrating CDA, which delves into the social dimensions that extend beyond language, into the analysis of conceptual metaphors in terms of meaning and cognition, enhancing the CMA theory. This allows for a more nuanced understanding of how metaphors operate within the complex interplay of language, society, and cognition in political communication.

In addition, it is noticeable that there is a clear similarity between the analytical procedures of CDA and CMA, which also partly explains the reason why CDA's three dimensions, "textual, discursive practice, and social practice", can be employed as three aspects of consideration for analyzing the factors influencing the adoption and roles of metaphors in political discourse. Fairclough (1992) describes discourse as "a complete unity that involves text, discourse practice, and social practice". The three dimensional nature of discourse demands that critical discourse analysis must also be three-dimensional. In this CDA model, text analysis refers to the linguistic analysis of content, while the analysis of discourse practice pertains to the processes of text production, distribution, and consumption, focusing on the factors involved in these stages, how they influence discourse, and how they interact with each other. For instance, this includes the identity and attitude of discourse producers, the media and means of propaganda, and the interaction between discourse producers and receivers as well as receivers' comprehension. Social practice analysis examines the relationship between discourse and social and cultural practices, analyzing how discourse practices are shaped by social structures, power relations, and ideologies, and how they contribute to these social structures, power relations, and ideologies.

These dimensions combine both micro-analysis and macro-analysis. The macro-processes of discursive practice are determined by the nature of social practice, while the micro-processes shape the text itself (Fairclough, 1992, p. 86). As an intermediary element, discursive practice can regulate the relationship between social practice and

text. These three dimensions are closely related, each being indispensable for discourse analysis, and each serving specific purposes. Subsequently, in his 1995 monograph, *Critical Discourse Analysis: The Critical Study of Language*, based on Halliday's (1985) functional linguistics, Fairclough proposed the methodology of critical discourse analysis: description, interpretation, and explanation. That is, the linguistic description of text, the interpretation of the relationship between text and discursive practice, and the explanation of the relationship between discursive practice and sociocultural practice. Similarly, Charteris-Black (2004, p.35) claims that CMA comprises three stages: metaphor identification, interpretation, and explanation. These stages parallel the procedure of CDA. The first step, known as metaphor identification, involves determining the presence of metaphor in the text and finding the relation between the source domain and the target domain. Metaphor interpretation involves establishing a relationship between metaphors and the cognitive and pragmatic factors that determine them (Charteris-Black, 2004, p. 37). The classification, organization, and arrangement of metaphors are the focus of discussion at this stage. In the final step, metaphor explanation, it is necessary to identify the social and cultural factors involved in their production and their social role in persuasion. Besides, the formation of conceptual metaphors, as well as the clarification of metaphors, are able to help explain the reason why they possess persuasive qualities (Charteris-Black, 2004). Therefore, identifying the roles of metaphors enables us to determine the ideological and rhetorical motivations behind them.

Importantly, both CMA and CDA serve the common starting point of investigating underlying attitudes or ideas within linguistic patterns and expressions. Critical metaphor analysis, is an approach for revealing hidden ideologies, attitudes and beliefs, thereby providing essential insights into the complicated connections between language, cognition, and social context (Charteris-Black, 2004, p.42). Similarly, critical discourse analysis is a way of revealing the dialectical relationship between language and ideology, as well as power, in terms of linguistic features and the context in which the discourse is generated, such as the social, political, economic, and cultural environments. It assumes that underlying intentions are connected with social purposes (Charteris-Black, 2013, p. 497). In essence, both metaphor and discourse function as mechanism for expressing individual attitudes and influence others' thoughts. Both CMA and CDA aim to explore the reasons for the usage of language, analyze the factors that affect the use of language, such as the hidden attitudes and ideologies of speakers or discourse producers, and underlying intentions or purposes that they select such expressions rather than others.

Despite there are many similarities, the two theories still complement each other. Fairclough's critical discourse analysis in particular emphasizes the importance of linking discourse structures and discursive practices to social and political structures at a macro-level. On the other hand, conceptual metaphor analysis focuses on textual comprehension and its relationship with social cognition. Social cognition exhibits inherent social attributes, as it is embedded in individual thoughts but shaped by shared societal practices within a community (Resnick et al., 1991). It also serves as the foundation for members of social and cultural community in a society. Thus, the combination of Fairclough's theory of critical discourse analysis and conceptual metaphors enables the analysis of metaphors used in political discourse to incorporate textual meaning better with cognition and society. In other words, the analysis of discursive practices and social practices in CDA makes CMA more systematic and comprehensive, emphasizing the role of social practices in shaping social cognition.

3. Theoretical and Analytical Framework

3.1 Purposeful Metaphors in CMA

Metaphors serve various functions in communication, highlighting the increasing necessity for a theory of metaphor that explains their prevalence in persuasive discourse. Considering this, Charteris-Black (2013)

proposed a teleological theory of metaphor and argued that metaphors in persuasive texts are best characterized as ‘Purposeful Metaphors’. This approach integrates cognitive theories, notably the theory of conceptual metaphors, with rhetorical and Speech Act theories to elucidate the reasons behind metaphorical usage, the mechanisms through which they are employed, and their subsequent impact (ibid., 497). Their purposes have been summarized into seven main categories (seen in Figure 1). This classification reveals the diverse roles of metaphors on communication, which extend beyond the expression of literal meaning and effects on textual coherence and issues simplification, spanning from cognitive understanding to emotional attitudes, evaluative judgments to persuasive trust, as well as contributing to the resonance or dissemination of ideologies, worldviews, and myths.

Figure 1. 7 Purposes of metaphors (Charteris-Black, 2013, p. 502)

Firstly, as a general rhetorical device, metaphors can quickly capture the audience’s attention and establish a bridge of trust between the orators and the audience through skillful language construction. Attention-capturing and interest-stimulating are prerequisites for other persuasive modes, and this trust is fundamental to successful communication, as it creates favorable conditions for the reception and understanding of information. Secondly, the heuristic function of metaphors plays a crucial role in simplifying and explaining complex concepts. By linking abstract or intricate ideas to things familiar to the audience, metaphors make these concepts more comprehensible and memorable. This simplification not only aids in the conveyance of information but also guides the audience to think about issues in specific ways, thereby influencing their perspectives and decisions. That is, it involves determining precisely what the metaphor brings to our attention and what it obscures (Charteris-Black, 2013, p. 503). For instance, the phrase *wind of change* subtly advocates for embracing change rather than opposing it, while the imagery of *river Tiber foaming with much blood* portrays immigration as a conflict and suggests that resistance is warranted. The predicative purpose of metaphors influences perceptions by implying positive or negative assessments of actors and issues. In other words, it provides a lexical resource for upgrading or downgrading positive or negative features (ibid., 504).

The three purposes mentioned above, from a systemic functional perspective, have been ideational. Nevertheless, metaphors also serve an interpersonal function by evoking empathy towards the speaker through subconscious connection, which is achieved by arousing feelings. This is done through pathos, humor, or intertextuality, as all these methods offer a shared emotional experience (ibid., 506). Empathetic metaphors touch the heart by eliciting emotional responses from the audience, creating a sense of resonance with the speaker. This emotional resonance is a powerful adhesive in communication, enhancing the audience's engagement with and memory of the information.

This aesthetic role aims to establish the speech as well-structured, harmonious, and possessing the aesthetic qualities of a musical composition. Metaphors interact with one another to create coherence at both a local textual level and intertextually, enabling speakers to craft an aesthetically pleasing style of discourse that contributes to their political identity (ibid., 508). Aesthetic metaphors add an artistic dimension to language and discourse, enhancing its appeal and persuasiveness by creating textual coherence. This pursuit of aesthetics not only enhances the expressiveness of language but also makes communication more captivating. Ideological metaphors carry deeper social and cultural significance in communication. By reflecting or constructing worldviews, they influence people's understanding and evaluation of social phenomena. The use of such metaphors is especially important in political discourse, as they can shape or reinforce specific ideological positions.

Lastly, metaphors play a mythic role at the social and cultural level by constructing participant roles and linking individual or collective actions to broader cultural narratives, invoking a heroic past to support present political agendas and future aspirations. These metaphors foster collective identity and propagate societal values and beliefs. Myth offers a narrative-based representation of powerful, intense emotions that are often unconsciously driven, such as grief, fear, happiness, and joy (ibid., 511). Charteris-Black uses the example of a journey to elucidate the mythic roles, emphasizing the unconscious, mythic appeal of journeys, that, in many myths, "embarking on long journeys towards some predetermined goal is an established means of assuming the stature of a hero" (2011, p. 324).

Metaphors serve diverse functions in communication, enriching language and playing key roles in cognition, emotion, evaluation, and persuasion. They are essential tools for understanding and shaping the world, as well as influencing thoughts and actions.

Charteris-Black (2013, p. 501) notes that different purposes of metaphors are analyzed at various stages; interpretation involves discerning specific meanings, representations, and evaluations (e.g., positive or negative), while explanation may explore underlying ideologies and political myths. It's crucial to understand that a single metaphor may serve multiple purposes, and these purposes interact in complex ways. Typically, a metaphor cannot be fully explained by just one purpose, especially since highly persuasive metaphors often combine a variety of interacting purposes (ibid.).

3.2 *The Integrated Approach for Metaphor Analysis*

However, the scholar also notes that this classification is not fixed or rigid; it is based on a limited set of examples he has examined. In other words, there may be additional roles or functions of metaphors that can be systematically organized within a framework.

Consequently, the three dimensions of CDA are introduced: textual practice, discursive practice, and social practice. CMA identifies the underlying purposes by scrutinizing the nuanced use of metaphors within texts and considering the context of political discourse, potentially revealing intentions. The three interconnected aspects of CDA elucidate political discourse in a more comprehensive and organized manner, complement the nature of metaphors, and provide both macro and micro perspectives to delve into the functioning of metaphors through

the cognitive link between the source and target domains. It is conducive to explaining and understanding purposeful metaphors, shedding light on why, how, and to what effect metaphors are employed in political discourse.

The first dimension is textual practice. As the name suggests, in CDA it refers to the analysis of the written textual content of a discourse. In current study, it refers to the presentation of the features of the metaphor itself and the discourse that contains the metaphor. Specifically, one of the focuses involves demonstrating the metaphor's inherent characteristics, which can be divided into two aspects. The first aspect is the superficial, linguistic-expression aspect, such as the role in enabling certain issue more accessible or having a sense of humor. The second is how the metaphor functions at the cognitive level, particularly its connection between the source domain and the target domain. Besides the factors inherent to the metaphor, the choice of metaphor is also related to the specific attributes of the text itself. Therefore, analyzing various elements, including structure, genre, style, and topics, becomes crucial when exploring the roles of metaphors employed in a certain context.

Regarding the “topic” in the textual dimension, it can be subdivided into Discourse Topics and Sentence Topics. The relationship between the two follows a rule represented by co-referential expressions and bounded by semantic coherence (van Dijk, 1977). The sentence topic derives from individuals' linguistic intuitions, and is dictated by the semantic structure of the discourse or the pragmatic structure of the context. The discourse topic is related to the macro-structure of the whole text, organizing the information within a passage at a global level, while sentence topic serves to connect fragments of information, indicating a kind of linear distribution of information (van Dijk, 1977, p. 60). The choice and usage of metaphor is concerned both with the topic of the sentence in which it is embedded and with the discourse topic that unifies the whole text, and these will be explored with examples later on.

The second level is the analysis of discursive practice. Within the theory of CDA, discursive practice analyzes how discourses are produced, distributed, and consumed in a specific social environment or in a particular context (Fairclough, 1992, p. 78). In the analysis of conceptual metaphors, there are still three stages, namely, production, distribution and consumption, while the analytical perspective involves all the people and entities related to these three stages. Firstly, at the stage of production of discourse, metaphor demonstrates the emotions and attitude, as well as ideologies of the producers of discourse. The same function in the same way at the level of dissemination and consumption of discourse. During the distribution process, the use of metaphors may also reflect the personal stances and ideas of the discourse processors involved in the communication. The mode and medium of transmission are also significant factors at this point, such as whether the discourse is conveyed through television or the internet, whether it is recorded, or whether it remains untouched like everyday conversation. Examining whether the metaphor used by the initial discourse producer is censored and adjusted or not during the transcription process also reflects the viewpoints and political stances of the transcriber during the distribution process. The final stage of discursive practice is the consumption of discourse, and the consumer of discourse in the context of political speech is the audience. It may be the direct audience at the site, but it also includes some hidden listeners. Since the discourse producer begins to select metaphors to be used, the intellectual background and social perspective of the expected or intended audience, as well as their standpoints and ideologies, are taken into account in advance. The audience, being the ultimate recipient and target group of political speech, must be closely related to the intended use of metaphor, since it constitutes the final stage in the discursive practice.

Finally, there is the social practice dimension for analysis purposeful metaphors. The analysis of social practice involves all aspects of society, such as political, economic and cultural background. The analysis of context, which was presented as a separate step in the revised CMA framework (Charteris-Black, 2013) but for which no detailed reasons were given, is placed here, as context also can be considered as a kind of social background that is currently taking place. For a more detailed explanation, in this case, “context” here refers to the “current context” in which the utterance is expressed, and the “context” becomes part of its environmental resources (Cap et al., 2011). Its nature is situational and dynamic, for which reason the current environmental factors should be taken into account, including time, place, participants, and causes and so on. For example, in this research, the context of the two speeches chosen is different from each other. One was delivered subsequent to a failed referendum in 2023, while the other followed a victory in the Australian federal election in 2022. Furthermore,

Social practice	Micro (situational)	time/ space/ participants/ causes
	Macro	background of society/politics/ culture/ economy

as previously mentioned, social cognition originates from social practice, implying that a specific socio-political or cultural context facilitates the formation of a shared ideology or cultural identity among a group of people. Therefore, when metaphor is employed to reflect a value or an ideology, it is crucial to take into account the factor of social practice.

There are also two additional points that need to be clarified. On the one hand, the introduction of the three new perspectives does not contradict Charteris-Black’s categorization of metaphor purposes, but rather is an integration of his categorization. For example, the textual practice perspective mentioned above, which involves demonstrating the characteristics of metaphor itself, incorporates the rhetorical purpose of the original categorization. There is also the predicative purpose, which expresses the speaker’s attitude towards the described object, and the empathetic purpose, which stimulates the audience’s emotions and elicits their empathy. They correspond to the production (discourse producer) and consumption (audience) aspects of metaphor in the discursive practice stage respectively. Another example, mythic and ideological purpose can be explained in terms of a group’s shared cultural cognition and national or political ideology at the level of social practice dimension. On the other hand, analyzing the purpose of metaphor requires integrating all three perspectives, as they often

Table 1. The New Framework for Analyzing the Metaphors

Dimensions	Sub-dimension	aspects
Textual practice	Metaphor	Linguistic dimension: humor, memorable, accessible Cognitive dimension: source domain→target domain
	Text	structure, genre, style, and topics...
Discursive practice	Production	discourse producer(s)/ orator
	Distribution	approach/ medium/ transcriber
	Consumption	(in)direct audience/ potential consumer

encompass and interact with each other. As mentioned earlier, when analyzing a metaphor, its purposes frequently interact. Through a detailed analysis of these three levels, we can detect the seven purposes proposed by Charteris-Black at each level. Taking the example *wind of change* from his monograph, which serves rhetorical and heuristic

roles, a textual analysis reveals that the metaphor “CHANGE IS WIND” is inherently short and easy to remember, making it easily distributable through media and accessible in discursive practice. For the audience, it is easy to understand and more accessible. From the perspective of discourse producers, they leverage the natural, unstoppable characteristics of wind to convey to the audience that change is of positive significance and should be embraced. If the specific background of the speech is shown, social practice should also be considered. For instance, the use of this metaphor might be due to a societal crisis where certain policies or the government urgently require change. Another example that is commonly used and prevalent in political speeches is to say that a certain POLITICAL EVENT IS WAR. Clearly, this metaphor “war” used here possesses the characteristic of being easily understood, which is analyzed at the metaphorical level in text analysis stage. This easy-to-understand feature is targeted to the audience who listens to the speech. Thus, it also involves the process of metaphor consumption at the level of discursive practice. Metaphor is employed to captivate the attention of the audience. At the same time, audience’s perception of WAR influences the selection of metaphors.

4. Methodology

In current study, two speeches delivered in different contexts by Australian Prime Minister Anthony Albanese are chosen. The first speech was delivered in October 2023 as a response to the unsuccessful referendum on indigenous rights. The second was a victory speech in May 2022, following Albanese’s win in the Australian federal election. Considering the various differences between these two speeches, the study aims to assess the applicability and interpretive strength of a modified framework by examining and comparing their metaphorical language.

The present study applies the three steps of critical metaphor analysis (Charteris-Black, 2004) to classify and analyze the conceptual metaphors found in Albanese’s two speeches, following the three categories of conceptual metaphors proposed by Lakoff (1980). The methodology unfolds in a sequence of steps. Initially, data is collected from the official website of Australian government. This is followed by a content analysis phase, where the speech discourses are scrutinized to uncover the metaphors. Subsequently, drawing on Lakoff and Johnson’s Conceptual Metaphor Theory and their classification, the metaphors are identified and the conceptual metaphors within the two speeches are categorized. A table is created to list the metaphors, and their frequencies are counted. Finally, the reasons and intentions behind the use of these conceptual metaphors are explored and analyzed based on the adapted framework presented in this study. Lakoff (1980) categorized conceptual metaphors into three types based on their distinct cognitive functions: structural metaphors, orientational metaphors, and ontological metaphors. Structural metaphors are considered the most complex as they enable speakers to comprehend the structure of the target domain by referencing the structure of the source domain, establishing a consistent correspondence between the elements of both domains. For instance, in the metaphor “LIFE IS A JOURNEY”, the abstract concept of “life” is understood through the framework of a “journey”, a familiar and relatable experience. Both life and a journey are processes that unfold over time and space, beginning at a starting point and progressing towards a destination. As for ontological metaphors, people are accustomed to perceiving abstract intangible concepts such as thoughts, feelings and activities, as concrete tangible entities. Entity metaphor, container metaphor, and personification metaphor are considered as three prominent types within ontological metaphors. Additionally, compared to ontological metaphors, orientational metaphors provide less cognitive structure for understanding target concepts. Instead, they help individuals construct another abstract concept using spatial orientation. Due to cultural and life experience, human beings have fixed cognitive

association with location words. Therefore, using orientational metaphors render orientational metaphors an effective instrument for grasping abstract concepts.

5. Results and Discussion

The identification of the conceptual metaphors in the two speeches is presented in the table below. This table illustrates the frequency and distribution of each type of conceptual metaphor, as well as the percentage they represent. In the column for conceptual metaphors, the different target domains are listed in descending order of frequency, separated by a slash.

Table 2. Conceptual Metaphors’ Frequency in Victory Speech

Types	Conceptual Metaphors	Frequency	Total
STRUCTURAL	LIFE/NATION’S FUTURE/ POLITICAL EVENT IS A JOURNEY	12(24.4%)	19(38.8%)
	PROBLEM/POLITICS IS WAR	2(4.1%)	
	NATION IS A BUILDING	2(4.1%)	
	POLITICS IS A STORY	1(2.06%)	
	POLITICAL ATTITUDE IS A RELIGION	1(2.06%)	
	DREAMS ARE PLANTS	1(2.06%)	
ONTOLOGICAL	LIFE/POWER/ECONOMY/PROBLEM/ CULTURE/BELIEF/OPPORTUNITIES IS AN OBJECT	12(24.4%)	25(51%)
	GOVERNMENT/OPPORTUNITY/HISTORY/ NATION/ECONOMY/POLITICAL ATTITUDE IS HUMAN	6(12.2%)	
	HEART/NATION’S FUTURE/PRIME MINISTER IS A CONTAINER	4(8.2%)	
	NATION/WORLD/POLITICS IS A PLACE	3(6.2%)	
ORIENTATIONAL	GOOD IS HIGH	3(6.2%)	5(10.2%)
	BAD IS DOWN	2 (4%)	

Table 3. Conceptual Metaphors’ Frequency in Referendum Result Speech

Types	Conceptual Metaphors	Frequency	Total
STRUCTURAL	POLITICS/NATION’S FUTURE/LIFE IS JOURNEY	9(18%)	17(34%)
	POLITICS/HISTORY IS WAR	4(8%)	
	HISTORY IS A STORY	2(4%)	
	POLITICS IS A SPACE	2(4%)	
	NATION’S FUTURE IS A BUILDING	1(2%)	
ONTOLOGICAL	POLITICAL ATTITUDE IS A NATURAL EVENT	1(2%)	29(58%)
	POLITICAL ATTITUDES/PEOPLE/BELIEF/NATION/POLITICAL PROPOSITIONS/POLITICS/DISCOURSE/HOPE IS AN OBJECT	15(30%)	
	POLITICAL EVENT/HISTORY/PROBLEM/GOVERNMENT/ PRINCIPLES IS HUMAN	8(16%)	
	SOCIETY/REQUEST/POLITICAL EVENT/HISTORY IS CONTAINER	4(8%)	
	POLITICAL STATEMENT IS POWER	1(2%)	
ORIENTATIONAL	SPIRIT IS MEDICINE	1(2%)	4(8%)
	GOOD IS HIGH	1(2%)	
	BAD IS DOWN	1(2%)	
	LOW STATUS IS MARGINAL	1(2%)	
	HIGH STATUS IS CENTRAL	1(2%)	

In
both

speeches, all three types of metaphors are present. Ontological metaphors are the most frequently occurring, constituting over half of the total in each case. Meanwhile, orientational metaphors have the fewest occurrences, at approximately 10%. This distribution is justified, as orientational metaphors are considered the most primitive among the three types, since spatial orientation is a fundamental concept essential for human survival. Furthermore, the percentage of ontological metaphors in the result speech is higher than in the victory speech, with one nearing 60% and the other around 50%.

Secondly, regarding structural metaphors, the JOURNEY metaphor is the most frequently used in both speeches. It is noteworthy that the journey metaphors in both speeches target the same domains, specifically analogies for “life”, “the nation’s future”, and “politics”. Furthermore, in terms of ontological metaphor usage, the three most commonly used categories in both speeches are the ENTITY metaphor,

PERSONIFICATION metaphor, and CONTAINER metaphor. Notably, the political domain dominates the most frequently used target domains in both speeches, encompassing terms such as “politics”, “political events”, “government”, “political attitudes”, “political propositions”, and related concepts. Moreover, the metaphor of “Nation’s future” appears several times across both speeches.

5.1 Similarities

To provide a more in-depth analysis of the reasons for the similarities and discrepancy in the use of metaphor between two speeches, the current study delves deeper into the three dimensions of discourse to analyze the metaphors. At the level of textual practice, the similarities in metaphor choices can be attributed to the fact that both speeches are of the same genre—political speeches. This genre often employs metaphors to convey complex ideas in a related and emotionally resonant way. The discourse topics of both speeches, being political in nature, dictate the use of metaphors that are politically charged and aimed at engaging with the audience on issues of governance, policy, and national identity. The targeted domains related to politics are a reflection of the speeches’ genre and topic, which aims to serve the political discourse and resonate with the audience’s expectations within that context.

On a micro level, each speech has an individual discourse topic, as indicated by their titles—one being a victory speech after an election and the other a speech following a referendum result. These specific topics influence the choice of metaphors to align with the particular messages and emotional tones intended for each occasion. For instance, a victory speech might use triumphant and forward-looking metaphors, while a referendum result speech might employ metaphors that reflect on the collective decision-making process.

In terms of discursive practice, both speeches are produced and disseminated by political figures, specifically the Prime Minister or his staff. The Prime Minister, Antony Albanese, delivers both speeches, which means his personal stances and ideologies are consistent across both. As a representative of the nation and a leader of the Labor party, his use of metaphors is likely to reflect national unity and the interests of all Australians, with a particular emphasis on marginalized groups. The mode and medium of transmission, such as television, internet, and radio, are also consistent for both speeches, which suggests that the metaphors are chosen with the understanding of how they will be received and interpreted by a broad audience. The consistency ensures that the metaphors used are accessible and resonate with the audience across different platforms.

Finally, at the social practice dimension, the similarities in metaphor use can be linked to the broader socio-political and cultural context. Both speeches are situated within the same national and political environment, which influences the choice of metaphors that reflect shared cultural cognition and national or political ideology. The metaphors used are not only a reflection of the current context but also contribute to shaping the collective understanding and response to political events. For example, if a speech is given in the aftermath of a societal crisis or a significant political event, the metaphors used are likely to be influenced by the need for unity, change, or a call to action, which are themes that resonate with the audience’s experiences and expectations within that social context.

In conclusion, the similarities in the use of metaphor between the two speeches can be understood by examining the interplay of the three dimensions. Each dimension contributes to the strategic use of metaphors that are designed to engage, persuade, and resonate with the audience within the framework of political communication.

5.2 Differences

One of the reasons that different metaphors are used, or different roles of metaphors can be analyzed between the two speeches, is due to the discrepancy in discourse consumption, which is significantly influenced by the

anticipated audience. This audience plays a crucial role in shaping the construction of the text and its metaphorical language. Producers in complex organizations (e.g. governments), craft their messages with an understanding of how these will be disseminated, transformed, and ultimately consumed by their intended audience. This is especially noticeable in political speeches, where the audience's expectations and the context of the speech can significantly influence the text and the choice of metaphors. In addition to the immediate audience, text producers also recognizes that certain "stakeholders" may pay closer attention to the speech than the general public.

The first speech, a victory speech following a federal election, is designed to resonate with all Australian citizens, reflecting the broad interests of the nation. It encompasses the collective spirit and triumph of the entire country. On the other hand, the second speech, which addresses the results of a referendum concerning aboriginal people, targets a more specific audience, namely, aboriginal individuals. This shift in focused audience explains the differences in metaphorical language between the two speeches. In the referendum result speech, we observe the use of orientational metaphors such as "LOW STATUS IS MARGINAL" and "HIGH STATUS IS CENTRAL". These metaphors not only describe the social standing of indigenous people but also aim to evoke a deeper empathy in the audience. They realized this by leveraging the audience's spatial perception and cognition of marginalization. By employing such metaphors, the speech aims to underscore the plight of indigenous communities and bring their struggles to the forefront of public consciousness.

Furthermore, the referendum result speech stands out due to its higher frequency of WAR metaphors, which appear twice as frequently in result speech compared to victory speech. In addition to understanding the referendum result from the discourse topic, the analysis of context in the dimension of social practice is also required. Albanese's result speech was delivered on October 14, 2023, which was prompted by the fact that a majority of people voted against indigenous Voice in parliament during Saturday's referendum. This outcome is not conducive to fulfilling his vow to narrow the gap in quality of life between Indigenous and non-Indigenous Australians, which he has promised when taking office. Therefore, the speaker's emotion in this situation is not joyful and uplifting like in the other victory speech.

WAR metaphor reflects the emotional inclination of the speaker. It embodies conflict and danger, creating a sense of tension and oppression. The linguistic realization of war metaphor in this speech indeed focuses on its negative aspects such as "reconciled" "reconciliation" and "hard-won", rather than positive elements like "win" or "success". The word "reconcile" means finding an acceptable way to deal with seemingly opposing ideas or needs and it often requires compromise, which is a process involving accepting an unpleasant situation on one side. The choice of these metaphors aligns with both the author's emotional tone and situational context.

The speech also employs unique metaphors of POWER and MEDICINE. "Medicine" is a substance, that you drink or swallow in order to cure an illness or treat an injury. The employment of medicine metaphor here aims to demonstrate a positive mindset despite the failure of referendum and provide a morale boost to the audience. Another distinction between the two speeches lies in the metaphor of HISTORY, which appears more frequently in the referendum result speech compared to the victory speech. This can be analyzed in terms of socio-historical and cultural aspects, related to Australia's intertwined history with its indigenous residents, who are an integral part of nation's history. They have "shaped" it (HISTORY IS A CONTAINER), co-authored its preceding chapter, and will continue writing subsequent chapters (HISTORY IS A STORY) alongside all the Australian people. The significance of indigenous people in history is further emphasized by evoking and utilizing the audience's existing knowledge and cognition of history and culture.

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, this research offers a novel and holistic viewpoint by examining the potential reasons for choosing and effects of certain conceptual metaphors across the dimensions of “textual, discursive practice, and social practice”. It underscores the feasibility and rationale of merging Critical Metaphor Analysis with Critical Discourse Analysis, which structures CMA more methodically. The significance of this contribution is evident through the thorough examination of two existent political speeches, which effectively illustrate the application of this integrated method.

The study’s findings indicate that the rationale and purpose for metaphor use in political discourse can be analyzed within three dimensions. This framework is also applicable to comparative studies, allowing for the identification of patterns across speeches, despite their unique characteristics. The research has uncovered both similarities and differences in the metaphorical language used in two distinct political speeches.

For example, both speeches exhibit a tendency towards structural and ontological metaphors, suggesting a preference for certain types of metaphorical expressions. In contrast, orientational metaphors are less common, suggesting a possible intended avoidance or strategic selection based on the intended message and audience. The high frequency of specific metaphors, such as the JOURNEY metaphor, can be linked to shared features between the speeches, including their genre, topic, and the processes of discourse production and dissemination.

However, the differences between the speeches are equally informative, leading to variations in metaphor selection. These differences can be attributed to aspects such as the unique contexts, intended audiences, and different cultural or social backgrounds of discourse consumers. The victory speech, aimed at a broad national audience, uses metaphors that convey unity and collective achievement, while the referendum speech, targeted at a specific group, employs metaphors that reflect the intricacies of social status and historical challenges.

In essence, this study contributes to the field by offering a more nuanced understanding of metaphor usage in political discourse. It demonstrates that an integrated perspective, considering the multifaceted nature of discourse, can provide deeper insights into the strategic employment of metaphors. By examining metaphors through the combined lens of CMA and CDA, this research has not only systematized the analysis of metaphors but also deepened our comprehension of how metaphors are used to construct meaning, influence perception, and shape public opinion within the dynamic realm of political communication.

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